

The Projection Operator in QIH: Angular Frequency as the Key to the Holographic Map

In Quantum Information Holography (QIH), the projection operator that maps the interference patterns of the singularity onto the event horizon is intricately tied to the angular frequency of Hawking radiation. This radiation, emitted as quantum fluctuations at the edge of a black hole, encodes the quantum state information of the singularity. Through the relationship between energy, angular frequency, and mass-energy equivalence, this projection operator allows us to observe the singularity indirectly by examining its quantum entangled counterpart: the event horizon. This process can be likened to watching a movie through a mirror, where the event horizon reflects the interior dynamics of the black hole.

The Role of Angular Frequency

Hawking radiation is quantized in energy, and each quantum of radiation has an energy given by $E = \hbar\omega$, where ω is the angular frequency, and $\hbar$ is the reduced Planck constant. Through Einstein's mass-energy equivalence, $E = mc^2$, the angular frequency of the Hawking radiation also encodes information about the mass-energy of the black hole:

$$\hbar\omega = mc^2$$

In QIH, this angular frequency serves as the projection operator, translating the interference patterns at the singularity into encoded states on the event horizon. The angular frequency captures both the oscillatory nature of the quantum states and their corresponding energy levels, effectively acting as the bridge between the singularity and the holographic screen.

Entanglement and the Mirror Effect

The qubits at the singularity are entangled with their counterparts on the event horizon. This entanglement ensures that every quantum fluctuation or interference pattern within the singularity has a corresponding state on the event horizon. When Hawking radiation interacts with the qubits on the event horizon, it serves as the medium through which the interior quantum states are mirrored.

Imagine a lattice of spinning Quantum State Vectors (QSVs) on Bloch spheres at the event horizon. Each QSV corresponds to a quantum state projected from the singularity. The angular frequency of Hawking radiation determines how these QSVs spin, encoding phase, frequency, and probability. This dynamic interplay creates a holographic image of the singularity, much like watching a movie reflected in a mirror. The singularity itself remains hidden, but its encoded information is fully accessible through the event horizon.

Mathematical Description of the Projection

The projection operator P in QIH can be expressed as a function of angular frequency:

$$\psi_{EH} = P(\psi_{bulk}) = e^{i\omega t} \psi_{bulk}$$

Here:

ψ_{bulk} represents the quantum interference patterns within the singularity.

ψ_{EH} is the holographically encoded state on the event horizon.

ω , the angular frequency of Hawking radiation, acts as the operator that maps bulk quantum states onto the boundary.

This mapping preserves the entanglement and coherence of the quantum states, ensuring that the holographic screen faithfully represents the singularity's interior dynamics.

The Holographic Movie: Understanding the Projection

The event horizon functions like a high-definition plasma screen, composed of Planck-scale qubits that encode the interference patterns of the singularity. These qubits are organized as Bloch spheres, each with a spinning QSV that captures phase and frequency information. The angular frequency of the Hawking radiation determines how these QSVs spin, encoding the curvature of spacetime, probabilities, and interactions.

Each snapshot of this holographic projection corresponds to a Planck time interval, capturing a moment of the singularity's dynamics. Over successive Planck times, the evolving states of the QSVs on the event horizon create a "movie" of the singularity's activity, projected outward for the universe to observe indirectly.

Connecting Physics to Perception

Through the projection operator, QIH unites the quantum realm with observable reality. The interference patterns at the singularity define the interior quantum dynamics, but it is their entangled projection onto the event horizon that allows us to perceive and understand them. This is not merely a mathematical convenience—it reflects a profound truth about the nature of reality. The reality we perceive is dependent on, and emerges from, the interplay of quantum states and their holographic encoding.

The angular frequency of Hawking radiation is the key to this mapping, linking energy, mass, and curvature in a seamless framework. By examining the event horizon, we gain insight into the singularity's quantum nature, making the once-hidden processes within the black hole accessible to human understanding. This holographic movie, projected through the mirror of the

event horizon, is a testament to the interconnectedness of the universe and the profound beauty of its quantum foundations.